

HEALTHY NUTRITION FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

O.R.Parpiyeva

Associate professor at the International Medical University
Central Asian Medical University,

Davlatov Hamidjon Dilshodjon ogli

An 11th grade student of the 13th comprehensive school in Fergana

e.mail: parpieva.odinahon@yandex.ru,

ORCID: 0000-0001-6223-103X

Fergana, Uzbekistan.

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Abstract. This article provides information about healthy eating for schoolchildren. School is a vital environment that can be used to influence the process of proper nutrition and to form correct skills and stereotypes in schoolchildren in this matter. Schools provide effective opportunities for carrying out work on health protection and healthy nutrition. It is the school age that is the period when the main development of the child takes place and the way of life, including the type of nutrition, is formed.

Keywords. school age, school feeding, image of the child, feeding problems, improper feeding.

Organized school meals are regulated by sanitary rules and norms and therefore largely satisfy the principles of rational nutrition. A disadvantage in organizing school meals is the preparation of the menu not so much taking into account the physiological need of children for biologically valuable substances, but taking into account the cost of products. And although this practice has recently been overcome, there is still a contradiction between the low price of school meals and the desire to comply with the established standards for the nutrition of children and adolescents.

Many students have a weak understanding of proper nutrition as part of a healthy lifestyle. The main problems with schoolchildren's nutrition are related to the violation of the nutrition regime outside the school walls, the abuse of chips, fast foods, crackers, sweets, chocolate bars, etc. Usually this is due to insufficient information or connivance on the part of parents. It is at school that children acquire a good half of their future chronic diseases, and often they are associated with forced improper nutrition.

The most important period of a person is school age (from 7 to 17 years) - a time of physical, intellectual, moral formation and active development. In the modern world, it is schoolchildren who take on the ever-increasing pressure of the information flow, affecting them not only at school, but also at home. In

addition to the school program, many children and teenagers additionally study in clubs, sports sections. To form and maintain physical, mental health and fully assimilate the school program, it is important to properly organize the nutrition of the schoolchild.

Many parents believe that in arranging a schoolchild's nutrition it is enough to rely on their own intuition and common sense. However, it is important to know the principles of healthy eating and the rules of food hygiene, the observance of which is of key importance in maintaining the health of the child. Firstly, a clear diet, taking into account the rhythm of physiological processes in the body and providing for three main meals (breakfast, lunch, dinner) and two snacks (second breakfast and afternoon snack). Eating at certain times promotes complete absorption of food and the prevention of gastrointestinal diseases.

For first shift students, the following meal times are optimal:

- ✓ First breakfast – at home at 7:00;
- ✓ Second, breakfast – 10:30-11:00;
- ✓ Lunch – at 13:00;
- ✓ Afternoon snack – at 16:30;
- ✓ Dinner – 19:00-20:00, but not later than an hour and a half before

bedtime.

For children studying in the second shift:

- ✓ Breakfast – 8:00;
- ✓ Lunch – 12:00;
- ✓ Afternoon snack – 15:00;
- ✓ Dinner – 20:00.

Secondly, an important adequate energy value of the diet, fully compensating for, but not exceeding the child's energy expenditure, taking into account the age, gender, physical constitution, intellectual and physical activity of the child. Depending on age, the average total energy value of the diet should correspond to: 7-11 years - 2300 kcal per day, 11-14 years - 2500 kcal, 14-18 years - up to 3000 kcal.

Thirdly, a balanced and harmonious composition of the diet is needed for all food components (proteins, fats, carbohydrates, macro- and micronutrients). The content of proteins, fats and carbohydrates should be maintained in a ratio of approximately 1:1:4 by weight. In terms of caloric content, this ratio will be as follows: 12-15% of energy due to protein, no more than 30% due to fats, and the remaining 57-60% due to carbohydrates, respectively. The content of plant and animal proteins should be in a ratio of 2:3. Fats - mainly plant.

It is enough to maintain a variety of food products that form the diet. The diet must necessarily include dairy, meat, fish, egg dishes, vegetables, fruits, nuts, vegetable oils, as well as grain products and bread. Ensuring high taste and aesthetic qualities of the dishes that make up the diet will help to avoid monotony and uniformity of the menu to prevent boredom.

Gentle cooking is also important, ensuring the preservation of nutrients in ready-made dishes (baking, boiling, steaming). Limit or eliminate frying and deep-frying. Allow enough time for leisurely eating. It is necessary to allocate at least 20-30 minutes for each main meal and 10-15 minutes for snacks.

Keep the kitchen clean, maintain your child's personal hygiene, and do not use contaminated food or water for food purposes.

If for some reason the child does not eat at school, it is necessary to provide your child with a set of products that compensate for the missed meal. Moreover, when choosing a snack, it is necessary to provide for its preservation of freshness for at least 4-5 hours. Accordingly, perishable products are excluded.

It is important to think about packaging that will preserve the integrity of the snack during the process (optimally - a plastic container). You can take with you fruit (apple, pear, banana) and nuts 30-40 grams, a sandwich with cheese or baked meat (important - do not use butter and mayonnaise, these components reduce the shelf life), complementing it with a fresh cucumber or carrot sticks. Cold tea (with minimal added sugar or without it), fruit drink, still water are suitable as a drink.

Skipping breakfast. The absence of a full breakfast is unacceptable for a schoolchild. Often, students justify their refusal to have breakfast by a lack of appetite and limit their morning meal to a cup of tea. But a lack of appetite in the morning is only possible if the daily routine or diet is violated. Perhaps dinner was too late or too dense and high in calories. Another situation is when the child went to bed too late, and in the morning prefers to devote time to sleep, sacrificing breakfast.

Eating mostly semi-finished products. Of course, ready meals that only need to be heated in a microwave oven make life much easier for parents. But such dishes are oversaturated with salt, animal fats, sugars, which cannot be considered healthy not only for children but also for adults. The use of semi-finished products is permissible occasionally, but the basis of home nutrition should be freshly prepared food.

Using high-carbohydrate foods as snacks. Colorfully decorated sweets (chocolate, chewy marmalade, wafers, cookies) or potato chips, salted nuts are attractive to children due to their affordability and rich taste. When making an independent choice when buying a snack, children most often give preference to these products. It is important not only to inform the child about the principles of healthy eating, but also to show him a healthy alternative to unhealthy snacks, for example, dried fruits, nuts.

Lack of fish consumption. On average, a Russian schoolchild eats fish dishes no more than twice a month. It is advisable to eat fish at least twice a week to provide the body with complete protein and iodine.

Insufficient consumption of vegetables and fruits. It is advisable to consume at least 300 g of fruits and 400 g of vegetables per day to provide the body with sufficient fiber and vitamins.

Drinking caffeine-containing energy drinks. Older schoolchildren are often guilty of this, using such drinks as stimulants of mental activity when preparing for exams. The combination of sweet carbonated water and caffeine has a detrimental effect on the gastric mucosa, causing the development of erosive changes, which can result in the formation of gastritis and peptic ulcer disease. The pronounced stimulating effect of caffeine on the central nervous system not only increases mental excitability, but can cause the development of convulsive syndrome.

If properly organized, schoolchildren's nutrition should provide the students' bodies with all the necessary nutritional resources and promote the full development of the growing body under conditions of intense intellectual stress.

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